

Women's Access to Education: Opportunities and Challenges for Empowerment

Mrs. Nilofar Shaikh

Assistant Professor, Vidhyadeep Institute of Business Administration,
Vidhyadeep University, Anita-Kim (Gujarat), India
alhazshaikh83@gmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

*Education, Challenge,
Opportunity, Women
Empowerment*

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14295360

ABSTRACT

Education has long been recognized as a fundamental human right and a powerful tool for social and economic development. Women all throughout the world continue to live in cycles of poverty and injustice because they are unable to obtain high-quality education. The current study is centered on the opportunities and challenges associated with women's empowerment and education. The study was conducting in Surat district. The descriptive research design was used for the study. With the use of structured questioners, 200 women were chosen for the primary data collection. It was discovered that the majority of women had completed their HSC and graduated. Majority of the women are connected with household work or doing private job. Opportunity like government scheme, less fees, free transportation and increasing job opportunities enhances the women's education, although women are yet facing challenges like family responsibility, traditional mindset, Gender discrimination and Low ability to bear Risk.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is widely acknowledged as an essential human entitlement and a potent instrument for fostering social and financial advancement. But for millions of women and girls worldwide,

getting a good education is still out of reach, which feeds the cycle of inequality and poverty. The present introduction lays the groundwork for a comprehensive investigation of the obstacles and prospects pertaining to women's educational attainment and its significant consequences for their empowerment.

Increasing a woman's or a group of women's spiritual, political, social, educational, gender, or economic power is known as women empowerment. In India, a wide range of factors, such as age, social standing (caste and class), educational attainment, and geographic location (urban vs. rural), significantly influence women's empowerment. At the federal, state, and local (Panchayat) levels, policies are in place to support women's empowerment in a variety of areas, such as health, education, employment prospects, gender-based violence, and political engagement. But there is still a big difference between what is actually done at the community level and how policies are being advanced.

The process of improving the economic, social, and political standing of traditionally underprivileged women in society is known as "empowerment of women." It's the process of protecting them against any kind of aggression. Women's empowerment means creating a political and social climate in which they can live freely from the oppression, exploitation, fear, prejudice, and overall sense of persecution that comes with being a woman in a system that has historically been dominated by men.

Women make up around half of the world's population, however India has a disproportionately low proportion of women compared to men in terms of population. They are not always placed on an equal footing with males in terms of social prestige. Women in Western nations enjoy the same rights and status as men in all spheres of life. However, prejudice and impairments related to gender still exist in India. She was concerned as a goddess at times and only as a slave at others due to the contradictory circumstances.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Completion of previous studies found that there are several literatures that highlight the Women's access to Education challenges and opportunities for empowerment. Some of the most important major studies are summarized here. Afsana (2017) studied revealed that the status, employment and work performed by women in society is the indicator of a nation's overall progress. Without the participation of women in national activities, the social, economic or political progress of a country

will be stagnated. Shettar (2015) reveals that women of India are relatively disempowered and they enjoy somewhat lower status than that of men in spite of many efforts undertaken by Government. It is found that acceptance of unequal gender norms by women are still prevailing in the society. The study concludes by an observation that access to Education, Employment and Change in Social Structure are only the enabling factors to Women Empowerment. Lakshmi *et al.* (2018) found that to grapple with the few challenges faced by the women in India in their family, society and nation like the dowry, female feticides, denial of inheritance rights, sale and trafficking of girls etc. Richard (2015) concluded that Women have shifted traditional assumptions about their roles and capabilities. There has been a marked change, and it has been for the better. Here some of the major challenges have been discussed. These challenges affect the growth and development of the women education in India tremendously. Bhat (2015) studied the education of women is the most powerful tool to change the position of society. Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family. To encourage the education of women at all levels and for dilution of gender bias in providing knowledge and education, established schools, colleges and universities even exclusively for women in the state. Alva et al. (2019) to founded that opportunities, changes and challenges related to financing, equity of conditions at access into and during the course of studies, and career choice and advancement.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Problem Statement & Operational Definitions:

The present study attempts to identify the Women's access to Education challenges and opportunities in relation to their empowerment.

3.2 Research Objectives:

- To study the socio-economic characteristics of the women.
- To identify the opportunities for promoting women's access to education in relation to their empowerment.
- To identify the challenges of women's access to education and their empowerment.

3.3 Research Design:

Descriptive Research Design was used in this study as it attempts to identify the Women's access to Education challenges and opportunities for empowerment.

Data Collection:

(i) **Primary Data:** The study is mainly based on Primary Data collected from women using the structured questionnaire.

(ii) **Secondary Data:** Secondary data have been collected from books, reports, journals, periodicals etc.

Sampling Design: A multistage sampling technique was used. In the first stage, three taluka of Surat district were selected randomly. In the second stage, four villages from each taluka were selected randomly and at the last stage, 10 rural women from each village were selected..

3.4 Sample Size: 200 Rural women from randomly selected three taluka of Surat have been surveyed in this study.

3.5 Limitation:

- The research was conducted in limited area.
- The time period for data collection was limited.
- Some respondents were not ready to provide personal information.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Variables	Categories	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age	21-30 years	56	28
	31- 40 years	102	51
	41-50 years	26	13
	51- 60 years	16	8

Education	Illiterate	08	4
	Below SSC	27	13.5
	SSC/Diploma	69	34.5
	HSC	71	35.5
	Graduate	25	12.5
Occupation	Household Only	77	38.5
	Farming	50	25
	Animal husbandry	36	18
	Service	28	14
	Self employed	09	4.5

Based on the frequency analysis of the responses of 200 women, as shown in Table 1, socio-economic characteristics of women were classified according to their age, education and occupation. Out of 200 respondents, the highest number of respondents belonged to age group of 31-40years (51%) followed by 41-50 years (13%) age group.

Majority of the respondents have education up to HSC that is 35.5% followed by 34.5% having education up to SSC/Diploma and 12.5% were having education up to graduates. 13.5% of them have studied less than SSC, while 4% were found illiterate.

In term of occupation, 38.5% of them were house hold only , while majority that is 25% women were involved in farming. 18% of these women have been involved in animal husbandry, and only 14% of them were doing services, only 4.5% women were found self employed.

Table 2: The opportunities for promoting women's access to education in relation to their empowerment.

Sr. No.	Opportunities	SA (5)	A (4)	N (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	CS	MEAN	Rank
1.	Safe Learning Environments	72(360)	58(232)	30(90)	24(48)	16(16)	746	3.73	2
2.	Scholarships and Financial Assistance	82(410)	64(256)	30(90)	14(28)	10(10)	794	3.97	1
3.	Education Programs Based on Community	56(280)	48(192)	35(105)	38(76)	23(23)	676	3.38	6
4.	Celebration of Achievements	69(345)	53(212)	27(81)	29(58)	22(22)	718	3.59	4
5.	Empowerment Training	46(230)	39(156)	43(129)	34(68)	38(38)	621	3.11	7
6.	Technological and Distance Learning	52(260)	56(224)	48(144)	30(60)	14(14)	702	3.51	5
7.	Investment in Girls' Education	61(305)	69(276)	32(96)	26(52)	12(12)	741	3.71	3

Women were asked to rank the different opportunities they experienced while pursuing their education. The weighted mean technique was used to rank the different opportunities based on the liker scale data that was gathered from the women. Table 2 demonstrates the three main opportunities that women have when it comes to scholarships and financial assistance, safe learning environments and investment in girls' education. Additional opportunities perceived by women were celebration of achievements, technological and distance learning, education programs based on community and empowerment training.

Table 3: The challenges of women's access to education and their empowerment

Sr.No.	Constraints	SA (5)	A (4)	N (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	CS	MEAN	Rank
1.	Gender discrimination	73(365)	69(276)	20(60)	23(46)	15(15)	762	3.81	2
2.	Female Infanticide	56(280)	46(184)	50(150)	27(54)	21(21)	689	3.45	6
3.	Early Marriage and Pregnancy	70(350)	64(256)	10(30)	32(64)	24(24)	724	3.62	4
4.	lack of financial resources	85(425)	60(240)	9(27)	28(56)	18(18)	766	3.83	1
5.	Family Responsibility	65(325)	57(228)	30(90)	34(68)	14(14)	725	3.625	3
6.	Limited Access to Resources and Infrastructure	71(355)	42(168)	36(108)	31(62)	20(20)	713	3.57	5
7.	Sexual harassment	20(100)	24(96)	86(258)	45(90)	25(25)	569	2.85	8
8.	Cultural and Societal Norms	31(155)	46(184)	50(150)	44(88)	29(29)	606	3.03	7

Women were asked to rate various constraints that they were facing while taking the education. Based on the collected liker scale data from the women, various constraints were ranked by using the weighted mean method. Table 3 shows that the major three constraints faced by women while lack of financial resources, gender discrimination and family responsibility. Other constraints faced by women are found to be Early Marriage and Pregnancy, Limited Access to Resources and Infrastructure, female infanticide and Cultural and Societal Norms.

5. CONCLUSION

Education has long been recognized as a fundamental human right and a powerful tool for social and economic development. The women around the world, accessing quality education remains a distant dream, perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality. The study focusing on various opportunities and challenges faced by women in relation to thire education. It was found that main opportunities felt by women were scholarships and financial assistance, safe learning environments and investment in girls' education etc. Women were also facing some challenges like lack of financial resources, gender discrimination and family responsibility etc. it is very important to prepared appropriate policy related to women education for their empowerment.

REFERENCES

- Rajeshwari M. Shettar (2015) Issues and Challenges of Women Empowerment, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, **17**(4):13-19.
- Afsana A. Sama (2017) Women Empowerment: Issues and Challenges, *Journal of Indian Psychology*, **4**(3)(2017):149-161.
- Desai and Mohiuddin (1992) Involving women in agriculture – Issues and strategies, *India Journal of Rural Development*, **11**(5): 506-648.
- Lakshmi and Jyothi (2018) Women Opportunities and Challenges in Empowerment, *Kaav International Journal of Arts*, (2):286-289.
- G.T. Govindappa (1999) Rural Women Entrepreneurship- Constraints and Strategies, *Kurukshetra*, **48**(2):11-14.

- Jhamtani (1995) Rural women: The Powerless Partners in Development, *Kurukshetra*, **43**(8):61-63.
- Richard (2015) Challenges in Empowering the Women Education, *Shanlax International Journal*, **4**(1):48-51.
- Bhat (2015) Role of Education in the Empowerment of Women, *Journal of Education and Practice*, **6**(10):188-192.
- Alva and Bhat (2019) Women Empowerment in India: Opportunites, Changes and Challenges, *EPRA International Journal*, **7**(5):5-9.
- Reshi, Sudha and Dar (2022) Women's Access to Education and its Impact on their Empowerment, *MORFAI JOURNAL*, **1**(2):446-450.